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**A MUSCULOSKELETAL STUDY OF ERGONOMIC RISK FACTOR
ASSESSMENT FOR MANUAL CABBAGE HARVESTING OF
FARMERS IN BADIAN, CEBU**

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This Undergraduate thesis entitled “**A MUSCULOSKELETAL STUDY OF ERGONOMIC RISK FACTOR ASSESSMENT FOR MANUAL CABBAGE HARVESTING IN BADIAN, CEBU**” prepared and submitted by **KRISTYL S. DIAZ, SHERLYN CARCELLER, MARK KIM PERALES AND GRECEL NIÑO QUISAOT** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree in **BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING (BSIE)**, has been examined and is recommended for acceptance and approval for **Oral Examination**.

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ABSTRACT

Background

A descriptive analysis that is taken to have established ergonomic risk factors among cabbage farmers.

Methods

For the evaluation of the prevalence of the ergonomic risk factors, the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA), Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ), and the Borg RPE Scale is used. It was conducted in cooperation with the cabbage farmers and not just through observation.

Result

The 3 instruments point out that the hips have the highest prevalence of MSDs among cabbage farmers. The workforce is predominantly male (83%), with a smaller proportion of female farmers (17%). Using the Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire, it was found that the hips/thighs had the highest prevalence of discomfort (18 cases), while the lower back had the lowest (7 cases). The Borg RPE Scale 10 highlighted the overall body, with a mean of 2.47, the next highest prevalence of MSDs was observed in the right and left upper legs, with a mean of 1.28. The Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) showed that the neck, trunk, and legs had the highest prevalence of complaints (Score A: mean of 9.197), while the shoulders, elbows, and wrists had a lower prevalence (Score B: mean of 7.2). Additionally, the REBA assessment indicated 100 % of the farmers involve very high-risk during cabbage picking.

Conclusion

Ergonomic tool are highly recommended. This tool used to prevent or minimize MSD among cabbage farmers when picking cabbages during harvesting season.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	PAGE
TITLE PAGE	i
APPROVAL SHEET	ii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	iii
ABSTRACT	iv
TABLE OF CONTENTS	v
LIST OF TABLES	viii
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
ANNEXES	ix

CHAPTER 1: THE PROBLEM AND ITS SCOPE

INTRODUCTION

Rationale of the Study	1
Theoretical Background	4
Review of Related Literature	7

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem	17
--------------------------	----

Significance of the Study	19
---------------------------	----

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method	21
Flow of the Study	21
Research Environment	23
Respondents	24
Instruments	24
Data Gathering Procedure	25
Statistical Treatment	26
Definition of Terms	27

CHAPTER 2: PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Process Mapping	29
Profile of the Cabbage Farmers	31
Perception of MSD to Cabbage Farmers	38
Level of Risk Experience by Cabbage Farmer	45

CHAPTER 3: SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings	50
Conclusion	53

Recommendation	54
BIBLIOGRAPHY	57
References	57
ANNEXES	68
CURRICULUM VITAE	72

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE NO.	TITLE	PAGES
1	Socio-demographic of cabbage farmers	31
2	Gender and Status of the Cabbage Farmers	35
3	Score using REBA	42

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE NO.	TITLE	PAGES
1	Theoretical Framework	6
2	Flow of the Study	22
3	Map of Cebu	23
4	Map of Badian	23
5	Process Mapping	30
6	Experiences of the Cabbage Farmers	38
7	Prevalence of MSD using NMQ	39
8	BORG RPE 10 SCALE	41

9	Very High-Risk Position	46
10	Very High-Risk Score	46
11	Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA)	47
12	Functionality of Cabbage Picker Tool	55
13	Proper Posture in using the Cabbage Picker Tool	56

ANNEXES

Annex No.	Content	Page
A	Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) Worksheet	69
B	Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire	70
C	BORG RPE 10 SCALE	71

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Rationale of the Study

Farming is often perceived as an accessible and healthy outdoor occupation (Thelin & Vinga, 2004). However, Farming is a physically arduous occupation and this places farm workers at potential risk of musculoskeletal disorders such as osteoarthritis (OA) of the hip and knee, low back pain (LBP), neck and upper limb complaints, hand–arm vibration syndrome (HAVS) (Palmer, 2002). According to Barneo-alc et al. (2021), Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) are one of the most relevant occupational diseases in the agricultural sector and their frequency due to high number of manual tasks. Farmers experience high rates of low back, shoulder, and upper extremity disorders, especially during harvesting. Akbar et al. (2023) stated that Southeast Asia (including the Philippines, Malaysia, Indonesia, Thailand, etc.) has many people who work in the agriculture sector which are exposed to various types of hazards. One of the most common health complaints of farmers during the harvesting season is related to work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs). The prevalence of WMSD will certainly affect worker productivity which can lead to decreased their productivity and also a decrease 1in the production of the country's agricultural sector (Akbar et al., 2023).

Manual harvesting demands the physical occupation of the vegetable farmers. There is an urgent need for improvement and validations of interventions to reduce exposures, and to prevent and monitor musculoskeletal disorders in vegetable farmers (Vcw et al., 2018). A variety of repetitive awkward motions (such as checking, holding, picking etc.) and bad postures (such as crouching, bending and kneeling, etc.)

sustained by workers for extended working hours may be the cause of the high frequency of MSDs in this industry. James et al. (2018) stated that numerous types of musculoskeletal disorders such as disorders of the back and neck, nerve entrapment syndromes, tenosynovitis, tendonitis, peri-tendonitis, epicondylitis, and non-specific muscle and forearm tenderness were consequences of the occupational risk factors in agriculture including static positioning, forward bending, heavy lifting and carrying, kneeling and vibration. At the same time, ergonomics interventions have the potential to reduce musculoskeletal disorders in vegetable farmers (Singh & Arora, 2010).

This study of ergonomic risk factor assessment for manual cabbage harvesting in Badian, Cebu, addresses a significant gap in existing research on musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) among agricultural workers. While previous studies have explored MSDs in various agricultural contexts, such as rice and vegetable farming, there is a lack of focused research on cabbage harvesting, particularly in the specific socio-economic and environmental conditions of Cebu (Cecchini et al., 2017). Moreover, different risk assessment methods have been employed, often overlooking the combined effects of multiple ergonomic factors, which may not be applicable to the specific context of cabbage harvesting (Cecchini et al., 2017).

This study aims to fill these gaps by providing targeted insights into the ergonomic risks faced by cabbage farmers in Cebu, potentially leading to improved safety and productivity measures. However, it is also essential to consider that while focusing on cabbage harvesting, the findings may not be universally applicable to other crops or regions, highlighting the need for broader studies in diverse agricultural settings.

This study is conducted in the Municipality of Badian, where the municipality is located in the Southern part of Cebu. Badian is a 3rd class municipality with a total population of 43, 735 people according to the 2020 census. The researcher gathered data with respective permission on the LGU in Municipality of Badian, out of 43, 735 total population of the municipality, 2,599 of them are registered farmers in the Municipal Agriculture Office (MAO). Badian was known as one of the source or suppliers of vegetables and fruits within the province and cities in Cebu. Cabbage Farming is commonly the source of livelihood for the people who are living near or at the foot of the mountainous areas in the Municipality of Badian. Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) are common most especially during the harvesting stage which is a common problem for farmers because of the extremely labour-intensive workload in agriculture. According to Jo et al. (2016), MSDs are more frequent among farmers, with more severe symptoms affecting the hands and forearms, lower back, and hips compared to less physically demanding non-farmer occupations which can impact substantially and result in long-term disability and income loss.

The researchers focus on the cabbage farmers to identify the MSDs of each individual during manual harvesting such as picking cabbage. The impact of MSDs on farmers during harvesting, planting, etc. is substantial and results in long-term disability and income loss (Jo et al., 2016). Moreover, the main objective of the study is to understand the experiences of the cabbage farmers and comprehend the essential structure of their psychological and physical state. The findings of this study will primarily improve their productivity and minimize the risk that they encounter when at work on their farm.

Theoretical background

The overexertion theory assumes that MSDs are caused by the amount of force exerted by the muscle to complete certain tasks. This means that MSDs might occur when the combined critical threshold for force, posture/motion, and exposure time are exceeded (Akweetelela, 2019). Cabbage farmers are involved in manual harvesting tasks such as picking. These tasks require a certain amount of body effort to be completed. According to Swanberg et al. (2016), farms should manage workers' hours or employ other worker to minimize the frequency of long hours as well as ensure that workers take adequate breaks throughout the day. Furthermore, it is necessary to assess workers' task to accurately assess the specific aspects of the work environment that lead to elevated MSD.

The multivariate interaction theory explains how workplace biomechanical risks lead to injuries. This clarifies how RTTs may sustain musculoskeletal injuries during patient transfers or positioning for therapy (Haley Griffin, 2018). "Work-related Musculoskeletal Disorders in Radiation Therapists: An Exploration of Self-Reported Symptoms" Data were gathered by distributing a countrywide online survey to a representative sample of radiation therapy technicians (RTTs) regarding work-related musculoskeletal disorders. The questionnaire asked about typical symptoms associated with labor in the field. Through data analysis, certain correlations between various factors, their incidence, and the anatomical location of musculoskeletal problems are also investigated.

Selvarathinam et al. (2013) stated that the Differential Fatigue Theory has shown varying degrees of force and effort are needed to accomplish various tasks. Muscle-specific MSD development is the assertion made by the differential fatigue theory. Thus, the rates at which MSDs develop in various muscles and the extent to

which they affect them vary greatly for each muscle. This is based on the amount of force necessary for each muscle group to execute each activity. Tasks that necessitate higher relative activity levels in certain muscle groups and associated connective tissues may cause/place muscles at a higher risk of developing MSDs. This is because muscles may become exhausted at a quicker pace, to a higher extent, and/or to a greater degree than other muscles and their associated structures.

This study is supported by the Repetitive Strain Injury (RSI) Theory. RSI is a generic term often used to describe discomfort and pain felt in muscles, nerves, and tendons that often develop with prolonged repetitive movement of the same body parts, eventually leading to an overuse of those body parts (Forsythe & Stanish, 2001). Farming is a way of life for most people. Farming is one of the pillars of life that holds society together from the very start. Having these MSDs cause injury to these farmers would lead to affecting the society negatively.

An injury, by definition, means mechanical disruption of tissues resulting in pain. Thus, it is a traumatic event in which the integrity of the tissue in question is violated and its mechanical order perturbed. The latter leads to pain in addition to inflammation and other biochemical responses, hence the difficulty in deploying these structures in any activity including occupational activities (Jain et al., 2001).

Farming involves a wide range of activities such as planting, harvesting, weeding, lifting heavy objects, awkward posture, and a lot more that require strength and flexibility, and thus having stress on the musculoskeletal system leads to MSDs. The goal of this study is to assess the ergonomic risk factors of farm workers in the municipality of Badian, Cebu.

Figure 1. Theoretical framework

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

1. Literature Review Summary

According to Anwer et al. (2021) Musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) are a degenerative and/or inflammatory condition that affect joints, muscles, cartilage, and blood vessels in the entire human body. The prevalence of MSDs is very high among laborious jobs such as construction workers, where awkward positions, prolonged works, high job demands, and mental stress are evidently present. Furthermore, MSDs are a challenge for individuals and organizations that would cost them their time and money.

One of the major reasons of disability worldwide are caused by Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs). The pain in the lower back specifically is the primary cause of disabilities around the world Bonfiglioli et al. (2022). MSDs can highly affect productivity and can lead to the loss of the ability to do work. This will then lead to losing a job which is not beneficial for every individual.

Safiri et al. (2021) stated that the rate of MSDs is higher in women than in men and increases in the oldest age group. However, men are much harmed by substance use disorders, transport injuries, and self-harm and interpersonal violence due to MSDs than in women (James et al., 2018).

According to Ng et al. (2019) Psychosocial factors are one of the experiences that contribute to MSDs among farm workers. The feeling of burden, repetitive tasks, social help, low job control, and fulfillment all boils down to these farmers in experiencing psychosocial problems, thus increasing the likelihood of MSDs. Furthermore, low job control, high job demands, high job strain, high effort reward

imbalance, low work time control, low social support, high workplace bullying, high hindrance stressors, low perceived fairness high role conflict, low job security, and interpersonal conflicts are risk factors that cause MSDs (Taibi et al., 2021).

A study found that 71.4% of manual-working farmers reported lower back pain, with other common areas affected including fingers (62.1%) and shoulders (56.4%)(Jain et al., 2018).

Common disorders include low back pain, upper extremity tendonitis, and arthritis, often exacerbated by repetitive movements and awkward postures (Benos et al., 2020; Steven et al., 2010).

Increased awareness and education about ergonomic risks are essential for improving farmer safety and productivity (Jirapongsuwan et al., 2023; Benos et al., 2020).

In the stages of crop cutting/harvesting and weeding operations, pain in the neck, shoulders, elbows and forearms, wrists and hands, low back, hips and thighs, knees, foot, and ankles are commonly seen. Bending over to perform tasks like weeding, harvesting and chopping crops, carrying crops, and planting seeds put a lot of strain on their shoulders and backs. Additionally, they discovered that farmers had to do more repetitive tasks than workers. Age was identified as a probable factor causing the risk of MSDs in upper extremity body regions based on multinomial logistic regression results, which is also consistent with most of the investigations (Jain et al., 2018).

According to Hwang et al. (2000), several health issues, such as hearing loss, musculoskeletal issues, respiratory diseases, and injuries, are affected by safety awareness and practices. Owner/operators of larger farms and those who are younger

generally have a greater propensity to alter farm operations. The models for significant modifications to machinery or processes and chemical substitutions are comparable. The age of the owner/operator and factors pertaining to the size of the farm (such as the number of employees and/or gross sales) are included in both models. It is less likely that older farmers have changed. It's possible that older participants are less adaptable or believe that additional health protection measures are needless after years of farming.

According to De Castro et al. (2014) stated that numerous issues were found to be associated with musculoskeletal disorders, heavy machinery handling and operation, heat and cold stress, respiratory exposures, pest control, socioeconomic issues, and language barriers. The results of this study shed light on the difficulties that Hmong refugee farmers face at work and can be used as a foundation for interventions designed by occupational health specialists to support this marginalized population. The main risks to safety and health that this project has identified are respiratory exposures, musculoskeletal disorders, injuries from heavy machinery (such as tractors and rototillers), heat and cold stress, and pest management-related activities. There are no official reports from the past that could be used as a comparison to describe the risk of occupational injury and illness in this population. The folktales incorporated various safety and health concerns, such as heat exhaustion, weariness, heavy lifting, repetitive motion, personal hygiene, and child supervision. The folktale educational intervention addresses the same issues that the current study found.

According to Nwuda and Kault (1986) stated that several studies have found a link between heart rate and working postures in a variety of occupations, including farming. Different body positions during tree felling have been observed to effect heart

strain in motor-manual wood harvesting, with flexed stooping inflicting the most harm (Tsioras et al., 2022). Data analysis revealed that tree felling meets the definition of heavy work, with a substantial relationship between heart strain and posture. Furthermore, among the local forestry workforce, the popular posture of flexed stooping is responsible for significant increases in heart strain.

According to Amoadu et al. (2023) stated that impact of climate change and heat stress on workers' health and productivity: A scoping review examine many risk factors for heat-related sickness, such as pre-shift dehydration, physically demanding work, excessive workload, limited job control, and high temperatures. It outlines adaptation techniques that may be utilized to reduce the effects of heat stress, such as regular fluid intake, resting under shade or in cooling facilities, modifying work hours, and increasing electrolyte intake. High temperatures have been recognized as a risk factor for heat-related diseases, and they can have a severe influence on the health and productivity of workers. High temperatures can significantly raise the likelihood of occupational accidents and injuries.

According to Tuure (1992) stated that determination of physical stress in agricultural work, the stress of dynamic work can be effectively evaluated using oxygen consumption or heartbeat frequency. Measuring oxygen consumption seems to be a viable approach of determining dynamic loads in agricultural activities. The goal of the study was to establish a methodology or set of approaches adequate for assessing the physiological demands of farm work. Other methods used included making three samples of the load of bail, lowering tomatoes, and motorized transportation of wood.

Working hours influence vegetable producers. According to Samosir et al. (2022) "Relationship between Work Position and Musculoskeletal Complaints among Vegetable Farmers", found that working hours were associated to musculoskeletal symptoms among vegetable growers. The statistical tests performed in the study revealed that there is no link between age and the working position bent during hoeing and musculoskeletal symptoms. Working duration, standing work posture while lifting weights, and sitting position during harvesting are all linked to musculoskeletal issues. It implies that the length of work and certain job roles may lead to musculoskeletal issues among vegetable producers. The study emphasizes the need for therapies and techniques to manage musculoskeletal issues among vegetable growers, taking individual job positions and length of labor into account.

As stated by Antle et al. (2018), "Lower limb blood flow and mean arterial pressure during standing and seated work: Implications for workplace posture recommendations", compared to sitting posture, standing posture was linked to greater levels of lower limb pain. The study examined variations in blood pressure, blood flow accumulation, and lower limb pain while performing a light-load repeating upper limb job activity from a sitting and standing position. When compared to sitting labor, standing work caused a mean increase in blood flow accumulation in the soleus and foot of 77% over time.

Tonelli et al. (2014) stated that due to their work-related exposures, elderly farmers are more susceptible to musculoskeletal disorders. Since many older farmers work past the traditional retirement age, the development of musculoskeletal conditions can increase the older farmer's risk of further injuries. Occupational health nurses with experience in agriculture can help farmers by assessing their safety and health requirements. Potential interventions include making farm equipment more

ergonomic, enhancing safety on the farm, and directing older farmers to programs that help them make safer farm modifications. Farmers' susceptibility to musculoskeletal disorders is influenced by a multitude of factors. Health care providers can better meet the needs of farmers and farm families if they are aware of the risks associated with farming and the farming culture. To lower the risk of musculoskeletal disorders and increase worker safety on farms, future programming and research should concentrate on these two areas. Due to age-related changes and occupational exposure, older farmers may face difficulties that increase their risk of disability. Occupational health nurses can recognize health problems, possible farm safety hazards, and community resources that can help older farmers.

Implementing ergonomic interventions, such as training on proper posture and the use of improved tools, can mitigate the risks associated with manual harvesting (Steven et al., 2010).

Jain et al. (2018) stated that manual harvesting is a physical laborious occupation in which musculoskeletal disorders mainly occur. In some instances, the risk factors for MSDs among harvesting farmers are not stated nor investigated properly in low and low-middle-income nations in the study. The research method and information were acquired by a set of questionnaires, they used the Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire and the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) to identify the various ergonomic risk factor of the farmers. Furthermore, the outcomes of the participants reporting pain were proven that at least one body part that has MSDs is prevalent among manual harvesting farmers.

According to Ng et al. (2014) production agriculture such as harvesting in oil palm plantations has been frequently associated with MSD which can affect significant

loss of productivity. The study tends to evaluate the viewpoint of the health of the workers, and the association between self-reported prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders, they used the Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire to collect socio-demographic background data and to determine the prevalence of MSDs. Moreover, they found that oil palm harvesters suffering acute MSD were likely to be still present to work and produced half less than their healthy counterparts. The acute MSD results by the Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire affect lower productivity loss and it is most crucial to take advantage of the health of each harvester on their palm plantation. They concluded that on ergonomics risk factors describing a high prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders have been reported to be associated with hazardous tasks.

Sa'Diyah et al. (2021) investigated reducing MSDs and the physical workload of a manual-harvesting peasant who owns small paddy fields doing their harvesting activity manually using a sickle and wooden-bench manual thresher. The harvesting activity using those tools make peasant work in bad posture, and it is done repeatedly over a long period which increases the risk of Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders (WMSDs) and physical workload. The research method knows the peasant's level of pain intensity during harvesting activity so they proposed using a digital human model to create more comfortable and safer work systems so that the Nordic Body Map (NBM) score, and work posture score assessed by using Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA), and the compression force of work biomechanics can be decreased. The NBM questionnaire is a body map that helps us to know which muscle feels pain as well as to know the level of skeletal muscle pain felt by the worker (Swanberg et al., 2016). The questionnaire enables us to compare the pain or injury level felt by different parts of the body based on its severity and to know its correlation with the worker's ability to work. The Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) estimates

body posture, especially the upper body. They discover that the pain or injury is felt by the peasant who does the whole process of harvesting activities, starting from cutting of paddy stem, transportation, and threshing until the packing of grains. They concluded that the physical ability of the human body will be weakened as the human gets older so they redesigned the process to prevent MSDs, and the peasant can work comfortably with a better posture that gives no harm to their health.

Mishra and Satapathy (2019) stated that the prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) of farmers not only reduces their performance, and efficiency but may also lead to more serious health consequences. The research methods of the rice cultivation process involve land preparation seeding and weeding, harvesting, and threshing process. They used a standardized Nordic Questionnaire to collect information and data (name, gender, age, and other personal characteristics and socio-demographic characteristics), and the RULA analysis was used followed by the CATIA V5 software. The researcher observed that almost all parts of the farmer's body such as the neck, shoulder, upper back, lower back, elbow, wrist, thigh, knee, and ankles were subjected to musculoskeletal disorders. Moreover, the application of the RULA technique for agricultural manual-harvesting posture analysis indicated that the farmers must focus on ergonomic principles by maintaining proper working postures in which the muscles will be at normal event, developing the required forces, reducing the stresses and possible injuries to the body parts.

Boriboonsuksri et al. (2022) stated that the research methods perceived physical exertion while working on a mango-harvesting farm with a modified Standardized Nordic Questionnaire. Physical risk level due to awkward posture was evaluated by the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA), and risk due to whole-body posture in association with the level of MSD risk was evaluated by using Rapid Entire

Body Assessment (REBA) score sheets. Moreover, they found that the final scores of the RULA and REBA assessments were different. The result showed that the highest prevalence of WMSDs and muscular fatigue occurred in the mango size-sorting task because the farmers were exposed to repetitive motion injuries while working for long hours. They concluded that mango size sorting should be the first task to be improved by proper ergonomic interventions with a man-machine system to resolve and reduce muscular fatigue problems among mango-harvesting farmers.

Ng et al. (2015) stated that the prevalence of musculoskeletal disorder (MSDs) among foreign labourers on socioeconomic background, occupational exposure social lifestyle, and postures adopted during harvesting task. The research method Ovako Working Posture Analysis System (OWAS) was used to determine the severity of awkward posture based on their videos on harvesting tasks recorded for each respondent. The analysis found that increasingly educated respondents have a higher risk of developing MSDs. They concluded that a higher educational level has been shown to be correlated with a lower risk of developing MSDs in the general population, the presented findings were consistent with the findings of adjusted odd ratio among finish farmers, where those who spent less time in education appeared to lower the risk of self-reported prevalence of MSDs. Based on their results, they found that the respondents who had less education had spent their childhood assisting their families in agricultural activities had a better adaptation to labour-intensive work tasks, and had developed higher tolerance towards fatigue and pain, and compared to those who had spent most of their childhood in school. Furthermore, they have been perceived as an awkward posture for the observer and the harvesters may not have experienced awkwardness due to adaptation (increased range of motion and tolerance) of the dynamic harvesting activities.

Shariat et al. (2018) stated that there are many potential training exercises for office workers to prevent musculoskeletal disorders. However, to date a suitable tool to monitor the perceived exertion of those exercises does not exist. The primary objective of this study was to examine the validity and reliability of the Borg CR-10 scale to monitor the perceived exertion of office exercise training. The Borg CR-10 scale was self-administered two times, with an interval of two weeks to evaluate the accuracy of the original findings with a retest. Face validity and content validity were also examined. This study found the Borg CR-10 scale to be a reliable and valid tool for monitoring the perceived exertion of office exercise training and may potentially be useful for occupational therapists to measure physical activity intensity levels.

Furthermore, the researchers employ the REBA, Nordic Musculoskeletal Disorder (NMQ) and Borg CR-10 scale due to their widespread usage in other similar studies. These ergonomics assessment tools, and questionnaire provides reliable framework for evaluating and addressing various aspects related to human posture and musculoskeletal disorder. By utilizing these, the researchers aim to ensure the validity and comparability of the findings in this study.

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to investigate the cabbage farmers doing manual harvesting such as picking cabbage in the Municipality of Badian and to determine the risk factor of ergonomics with regards to musculoskeletal disorders. It encompasses the goal to obtain knowledge regarding risk factor of each cabbage farmers. The researcher's investigation contributes most especially to all cabbage farmers in the Municipality of Badian and in other locality that suffered the same risk factor of ergonomics in doing manual picking of the cabbage farmers.

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of vegetable farmers?
 - 1.1 Age.
 - 1.2 Height.
 - 1.3 Weight.
 - 1.4 Experience.
 - 1.5 Gender.
 - 1.6 Status.
2. What are the MSD's experienced by the farmers upon doing manual harvesting?
3. What level of risk hazard of farmers in cabbage picking?

4. What are the most possible interventions on reducing the risk of MSDs in cabbage farmers doing manual harvesting?

This study will shed light on the difficulties these farmers encounter in connection to MSDs and will aid in the development of interventions that aim to improve the well-being and standard of living of this crucial workforce.

Significance of the Study

Farmers. This study can enhance the health of cabbage farmers using manual harvesting by detecting and evaluating the risk factors for musculoskeletal disorder in Badian, Cebu. Improving the health and productivity of the agricultural workers can result from addressing these risk factors.

Community. There could be wider ramifications for the general health of the cabbage farmers using manual harvesting in Badian, Cebu. Lowering the strain on healthcare systems and enhancing health of each individual can be achieved by preventing and treating musculoskeletal disorders among to the cabbage farmers.

LGU. Sustainable agriculture is a global concern. Understanding the challenges encountered by the cabbage farmers doing manual harvesting, including musculoskeletal disorders, and can inform practices that support the long-term sustainability of agriculture in the Municipality of Badian, Cebu.

Occupational Health and Safety. This research contributes to the understanding of the occupational health and safety issues encountered by cabbage farmers using manual harvesting in Badian, Cebu. It clarifies the specific musculoskeletal disorders that may affect this population, helping to develop strategies for prevention and intervention.

Agricultural Industry. This study emphasizes the importance of addressing ergonomic risk factors in manual cabbage harvesting, in which can lead to improve the health of the worker and productivity. By reducing musculoskeletal disorders among farmers, it can benefit from increased

efficiency, lower labor turnover, and reduced healthcare costs, contributing to the overall sustainability and growth of the sector.

Other Researchers. Lastly, the researcher's study can be used as a potential reference for future researchers with the intention of identifying the Musculoskeletal Disorder (MSD) experience of the cabbage farmer upon doing manual harvesting.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1.1 Method

This study is done through a quantitative approach with the use of a descriptive method. Nassaji (2015) stated that Descriptive research aims to describe a population, situation or phenomenon accurately and systematically, which call a wide variety of research methods to investigate one or more variables. Descriptive research is an appropriate method which aim to identify, characteristics, frequencies, trends and categories. The point to be observed in the study is the intervention in which data is gathered for the usual methods of farmers practice in harvesting cabbage.

1.2 Research Flow of the Study

The research ensured that the input, process, and output are interconnected and coherent. It contains the profile of the respondents. It also contains data and information obtained by the Nordic Map Questionnaire (NMQ), Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA), and Borg CR-10 scale. The data needed would then be acquired through the process of tabulation, analyzation, interpretation, and statistical treatment using Mean, Median, and Standard Deviation.

Figure 2. Flow of the Study

1.3 Research Environment

This study's research locations are in Badian, Cebu. The island province of Cebu has the coastal municipality of Badian. Moalboal borders it on the north, Dalaguete on the east, Alegria on the south, and the Tanon Strait on the west. The municipality makes up 2.23 percent of Cebu's total area, with an area of 110.07 square kilometers (42.50 square miles). Badian is a 3rd class municipality with a total population of 43, 735 people according to the 2020 census. The researcher gathered data with respective permission on the LGU in Municipality of Badian, out of 43, 735 total population of the municipality, 2,599 of them are registered farmers in the Municipality of Agriculture Office (MAO).

Figure 3. Map of Cebu

Figure 4. Map of Badian

1.4 Respondents:

The respondents of this study will be selected based on a number of criteria to ensure that the research findings are valid and reliable. The primary criterion is that the respondents must be farmers in Badian, Cebu, who are knowledgeable and are actively engaged in harvesting cabbage. This criterion ensures that the respondents have direct experience and knowledge that relates to the research topic, which provides the researchers relevant insights and data.

To obtain a representative sample, 30 respondents from these farmers will be chosen using purposive sampling. The age range of the chosen respondents ranges from 20 to 60 years old, which represents a diverse demographic that includes both younger and older farmers. This age range captures the wide array of perspectives and experiences that relates to cabbage farming. Additionally, respondents will be selected regardless of gender, ensuring inclusivity and diversity in the sample.

Another critical criterion is the geographical location, as the study focused specifically on farmers within Badian, Cebu. This guarantees that the results are applicable to the agricultural environment of Badian, Cebu and neighboring municipalities and can be utilized in establishing local farming methods and rules and procedures. Furthermore, all 30 respondents must be available and willing to participate throughout the study period, ensuring the consistency and reliability of the collected data.

1.5 Instrument

The main instrument in this investigation would be with the use of Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire designed by Kuorinka et al. (1987). The data is obtained through calculating the regional scores, where each body region have

separate scores. With zero being no pain or discomfort and four being very severe pain or discomfort.

Furthermore, the study is also anchored to the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) designed by Hignett and Mcatamney (2017), for us to identify the risk factors. The REBA Score one being negligible and eleven to 15 being very high-risk level.

Additionally, the physiological responses of the farmers are rated with the Borg CR-10 scale with six being no exertion at all, and 10 being exhausted (Borg et al., 2014).

1.6 Data Gathering Procedure

After the validation of the instrument, the researchers secured a written permit from the mayor of Badian, Cebu. Records from the office are useful enough for the needed data on the total number of vegetable farmers who have cabbage vegetation in the area, including their sex and age. After being given permission, the researchers explained the purpose of the study to the selected respondents, and then they made sure each participant matched their predefined criteria. The researchers collected the data by means of a survey questionnaire that included their sex, age, and number of years working in the field. The problems encountered by the respondents will be identified through the second part of the survey questionnaire that was given to them, including rating scales, which allow farmers to self-report the perceived strain or effort experienced during cabbage harvesting, providing insights into the perceived physical effort during a task.

The three tools that is used includes the Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire, will be administered face-to-face to ensure that the questions are clear and that participants feel comfortable providing correct information, the Rapid Entire Body

Assessment (REBA) will be performed using on-site observations in which cabbage growers' postures will be examined while doing various tasks in the field, and finally, under Borg CR-10 scale, questionnaires will be handed to cabbage farmers during or after various tasks, with farmers self-reporting their perceived effort levels on the scale.

The researchers are committed to following ethical standards in our research to guarantee the well-being and rights of our participants. The researchers will seek informed permission from each participant prior to data collection by fully explaining the study's goal, methods, and any implications. Confidentiality will be rigorously maintained through the use of anonymized data to protect the privacy of participants. The papers were examined, tallied, interpreted, and analyzed after the respondents being observed and the survey questionnaires were completed.

1.7 Statistical Treatment

The data from NMQ scores from the different body regions, REBA scores for various harvesting tasks, and Borg CR-10 scale during harvesting activities are gathered. The study used the Descriptive statistics method, and the researchers calculated the mean, median, and standard deviation of the NMQ, REBA, and Borg CR-10 scale. The researchers use histograms, boxplots, and bar graphs to visualize data and compare the distribution of results between groups and across multiple time points.

These methods allow the researchers to identify the Ergonomic risk factors of the cabbage farmers during the harvesting stage to be intervened.

1.8 Definition of Terms

Borg CR-10 scale. One of the questionnaires which measures the perceived physical effort or exertion during the manual task. It evaluates how the cabbage harvesting for the farmers, assessing the level of strain on their bodies to correlate with musculoskeletal disorders.

Cabbage Farmers. The primary subjects of this study, which engaged in manual cabbage harvesting. The study examines how their daily task, including repetitive bending, lifting, and cutting, contribute to ergonomic risk factors and the development of musculoskeletal disorders.

Farming. It highlights the physical labor involved in harvesting cabbages, focusing on how ergonomic risks and manual harvesting impact the health and productivity of the cabbage farmers.

Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire. A questionnaire which used to identify and assess the prevalence and severity of musculoskeletal pain or discomfort among cabbage farmers.

Manual harvesting. It involves collecting cabbages by hand, typically using knives or other tools. And it is a labor-intensive and often involves awkward postures, repetitive motions, and heavy lifting, musculoskeletal disorders.

Musculoskeletal Disorder. It encompasses injuries or discomfort affecting the muscle, tendons, ligaments, and bones due to repetitive strain, awkward postures, or overexertion.

Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA). It evaluates the ergonomic risk associated with manual cabbage harvesting. REBA is applied to assess the postures, force, and movement patterns of the cabbage farmers during manual harvesting to identify high-risk activities.

CHAPTER 2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this chapter, the researcher presents and discusses the results of the data collected through survey and questionnaire of the cabbage farmers in doing manual harvesting in the Municipality of Badian. The results of this study are illustrated using tables and graph.

Presentation of Results and Discussion

The following section presents detailed findings on the musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) experienced by cabbage farmers engaged in manual harvesting.

I. Process Mapping

In figure 5, it shows the process mapping of doing manual cabbage harvesting. Harvesting cabbage is a simple yet physically intensive task. It all starts with a walk to the cabbage farm. Once there, the first task is to check which cabbages are ready for harvesting. This involves gently holding the head of each cabbage to see if it has reached the right size and firmness. If a cabbage is ready, you bend or crouch down to reach its stem. Using a sharp knife, you carefully cut the cabbage from the base of the plant.

After cutting, the next step is to clean the cabbage by removing any excess leaves. Once cleaned, you place the cabbage on the ground. Then, you stand up and scan the area for more cabbages. This involves checking each cabbage by holding its head to determine if it is ready for harvest. If there are more cabbages within reach, you repeat the process: bending, cutting, cleaning, and placing the cabbage on the

ground. If there are no more cabbages within immediate reach, you stand up and scan the area again. This cycle continues until all the cabbages in the field are harvested.

Figure 5. Process Mapping

The results presented in table 1 are the age, height, weight, experiences (years), how often they work in a week and how many hours they work in a day. Additionally, the results from various instruments such as Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ), Borg RPE 10 Scale and Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) used to identify the prevalence of MSDs, the level of risk factors, and the impact of MSDs among these farmers are shown through charts and tables.

II. Profile of the Cabbage Farmers

Table 1. Socio-demographic of cabbage farmers

Specifies	Maximum	Minimum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	15 yrs. old	74 yrs. old	32.23yrs. old	13.82 yrs. old
Height	166 cm	141 cm	155 cm	6.26 cm
Weight	73 kg	43 kg	56.27 kg	9.08 kg
Experience	1 (year)	44 (years)	14.93 (years)	11.82 (years)
How often they work in a week	2 (days)	7 (days)	5.53 (days)	1.43 (days)
How many hours they work in a day	4 hours	8 hours	6.30 hours	1.30 ours

A. Age of the Cabbage Farmers

The mean age of cabbage farmers is 32.23 years, which is significantly lower than the average farmer's age of 57–59 years reported by Dinco (2024) for farmers in the Philippines. This age difference suggests a generational shift, with younger individuals increasingly taking up roles in agriculture. This shift could influence the types and prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), as younger farmers may experience different work-related challenges compared to their older counterparts. According to Boriboonsuksri et al. (2022), musculoskeletal problems are common among farmers, with a particularly high prevalence of MSDs among older workers, especially in relation to back pain. The higher susceptibility of older farmers to work-related MSDs due to factors such as decreased muscle strength, endurance, and overall functional capacity, making them more vulnerable to injuries. These findings highlight the importance of considering age-related differences when assessing MSD risks in the agricultural sector. The study by Dinco (2024) reinforces this perspective by showing that as the farming population ages, the burden of MSDs may increase unless preventive measures are taken. Therefore, the involvement of younger farmers in agriculture could potentially lead to a shift in the patterns of MSDs, necessitating updated strategies for prevention and management tailored to different age groups.

B. Height of the Cabbage Farmers

The mean height of 155 cm (shown on table 1) among cabbage farmers has significant implications for the development of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) during the manual harvesting process. According to Zubia et al. (2010) the average height of farmers is 161.8 which lower to the result of the mean on cabbage farmers. Harvesting cabbages often requires bending down and working close to the ground.

This constant bending leads to awkward postures, particularly when they have maintained a stooped position for extended periods, increasing the risk of developing lower back pain and other MSDs. Moreover, repetitive stooping or squatting puts added strain on the lower back, knees, and shoulder, contributing to cumulative trauma over time. The higher the height of the cabbage farmer the more they bend their body in manual picking of cabbage. Guntoro et al. (2023) state that it was found out that different working profiles can use variability in physical body dimensions. The correlation of body dimensions was also obtained with respect to the standing height. This means that some of the body measurements have positive correlation with the standing height.

C. Weight of the Cabbage Farmers

The average weight of the cabbage farmers is 56.27 kg (shown in table 1), indicating that most of the cabbage farmers are around this weight which ranges 43 kg to 73 kg shows the variation in weight among the farmers. A standard deviation of 9.08 kg suggests that there is a moderate amount of spread in the weights, meaning that while most farmers are close to the average, there are some who weigh significantly more or less. The average weight of cabbage farmers is within a healthy range for most individuals. This variation in weight, combined with the physical demands of manual harvesting, could contribute to differing levels of strain on the body and potentially influence the risk of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs). The bigger the weight of a cabbage farmer the more they put weight in their body when bending their body in manual picking of cabbage. The study conducted by James et al. (2018), "Physical Work and Health in Agriculture" (2014) highlights the potential impact of physically demanding agricultural tasks on body composition and overall health. The study found that agricultural labor can lead to musculoskeletal disorders,

cardiovascular diseases, and respiratory problems. These health issues can affect physical development and contribute to variations in height and weight.

D. Experiences of the Cabbage farmers

The cabbage farmers had an average of 14.93 years of farm work experience, as indicated in Table 1, which is lower than the 18 years reported by the National Center for Farmworker Health Inc. (NCFH) for US agricultural workers. This disparity could be influenced by regional differences in economic conditions and farming practices. Supporting studies suggest that areas with higher levels of mechanization and better access to resources often see longer careers among farmers. This shorter duration might reflect the physical demands and challenges specific to cabbage farming in the studied region. Consequently, these factors may lead to earlier career shifts compared to those in more resource-rich agricultural environments.

The study found that the average number of days farmers work per week is 5.53, with an average of 6.30 hours per day (Table 1). This contrasts with January et al. (2022) findings, which suggest that during peak farming seasons, such as planting, growing, and harvesting, farmers typically work 6 to 7 days a week, with daily hours ranging from 8 to 9.5. The difference in working hours between this study and Clerk's might be attributed to the younger demographic of the farmers surveyed, many of whom have other commitments like education, limiting their availability for farm work. Additionally, younger farmers prioritize other activities over extended work hours, unlike older farmers, who might have fewer competing responsibilities. The similarity to the cabbage farmers' working hours could indicate that specific crops or farming methods influence time allocation. The shorter working hours observed in this study may reflect a trend among younger farmers to balance farming with other aspects of

their lives. These findings underscore the importance of considering age and other socio-demographic factors when analysing labour patterns in agriculture. Further research could explore how these factors impact productivity and well-being in the farming community.

Table 2. Gender and Status of the Cabbage Farmers

	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Gender		
<i>Female</i>	5	17%
<i>Male</i>	25	83%
<i>Total</i>	30	100%
Status		
<i>Single</i>	12	40%
<i>Married</i>	18	60%
<i>Widow</i>	0	0
<i>Total</i>	30	100%

E. Gender of the Cabbage Farmers

Table 2 shows the results of the gender and status of the cabbage farmers. The gender of the cabbage farmers is that out of 30 participants, 83% are male and 17% are female. This is supported by the study of the Statista Research Department (2023), which states that the proportion of employed males in agriculture in relation to total male employment was 29.9%. In comparison, female agriculture workers made up 15.7% of the total female workforce, which means that male workers in agriculture were greater than female workers, as also proven by our gathered data. Additionally,

there are more men in the agriculture industry because of the widespread belief that farming are physically demanding jobs that require male strength. And the societal norms and traditional gender roles often position men as the primary controllers of food systems, leading to a male-dominated workforce in agriculture (Ankrah et al., 2020).

F. Status of the Cabbage Farmers

The status shows that most of the cabbage farmers was married with an overall total of 18 participants and 12 of them are single based on the result of gathered data (shown in table 2). And according to Roa et al. (2022) most of the farmers are married with an overall percentage of 78.05% as compared to single and widow or separated status. This implies that married individuals tend to work more hours than those who are unmarried or separated because they often have greater financial responsibilities. Married people may need to provide for their families, which can include children, a spouse, and household expenses, leading them to work longer hours to meet these obligations. Additionally, the stability and support system provided by a marriage may enable them to commit more time to their work.

G. Experiences of the Cabbage Farmers with regards to MSD.

The results indicated the prevalence of musculoskeletal disorder in the past 7 days and 12 months where the highest prevalence was found in one or both hips/thighs (shown in fig. 6), respectively. In the last 12 months, the highest prevalence of MSDs was reported in the hips/thighs, wrists/hands, and shoulders. The hip/thigh region's frequent discomfort can be attributed to the repetitive bending during cabbage picking. These activities place significant strain on the lower body, particularly the hip

flexors and thigh muscles. Additionally, the wrists and hands are constantly engaged in cutting and handling cabbage, leading to overuse injuries such as tendinitis or carpal tunnel syndrome. The shoulder discomfort likely stems from the repetitive overhead movements which can cause strain or impingement in the shoulder joints. According to Boriboonsuksri et al. (2022) the highest prevalence of musculoskeletal disorder of farmers in Thailand was found in the lower extremities (65.4%), lower back (42.6%) and shoulder (29.9%) because most of the farmers exposed to prolonged static postures such as sitting, bending, kneeling, and squatting which cause muscles to become tense over long period of time. Keeping a certain body posture without the movement of the corresponding joints can cause muscles to contract. In contrast, over the last 7 days, the prevalence of MSDs shifted, with the hips/thighs, knees, and upper back being the most affected areas. The continued high prevalence in the hips/thighs reinforces the idea that the demands of cabbage harvesting place ongoing stress on these regions. However, the emergence of knee discomfort in the last 7 days highlights the cumulative impact of prolonged squatting and kneeling, common postures during harvesting. These positions can exacerbate wear and tear on the knee joints, leading to pain and inflammation. The upper back's increased prevalence points to the physical toll of sustained forward bending and the strain on the upper spinal muscles and ligaments as farmers continuously work in awkward positions.

Cabbage farmers experience significant musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) due to the repetitive and strenuous nature of their daily harvesting tasks. They often spend long hours bending over to cut cabbages and twisting their bodies to reach different readily harvested cabbages. In the past 12 months, chronic strain has primarily affected their wrists, hands, and shoulders from repetitive cutting motions. Recently,

acute stress has shifted to their knees and upper back, reflecting the immediate demands of continuous bending, and maintaining awkward postures. Typically, these farmers work until they finish harvesting all the cabbage in a designated area, averaging 5.53 days per week and 6.30 hours per day. This finding agrees with the study of (Boriboonsuksri et al., 2022) which also indicated prolonged static postures such as sitting, bending kneeling, twisting and squatting which can cause musculoskeletal injury in cabbage farmers.

Figure 6. Experiences of the Cabbage Farmers

III. Perception of MSD to Cabbage Farmers

A. Using Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ)

The study's results, based on the Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ) (shown in fig. 7), indicate the prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders (MSD) in the

hips and thighs of cabbage farmers engaged in picking, with 18 cases reported. This high incidence suggests that the repetitive motions, such as bending and sustained awkward postures required during harvesting, place significant strain on these areas. In contrast, the lower back showed the lowest prevalence, with only 7 cases, possibly indicating that while the lower back is under stress, it is less directly impacted by the specific actions required in this type of manual labor.

These findings are consistent with the research of Arcury et al. (2007), who also observed a high prevalence of MSD in the legs of agricultural workers engaged in similar tasks. Their study reinforces the notion that the lower body, particularly the hips and thighs, bears the brunt of the physical strain in harvesting activities. This pattern suggests that the repetitive and physically strenuous nature of the work primarily impacts the hips and thighs. These studies underscore the need for targeted ergonomic interventions and preventive strategies to reduce the risk of MSD, particularly in the hips and thighs, to enhance both the health and productivity of cabbage farmers.

Figure 7. Prevalence of MSD using NMQ

B. Using Borg RPE Scale 10

The study indicates that cabbage farmers experience the highest prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) in the overall body, with a mean of 2.47 on the Borg RPE Scale 10 (shown in fig. 8). This suggests that the physical demands of cabbage harvesting place moderate strain on the body, aligning with findings in other agricultural sectors where repetitive tasks contribute to overall discomfort (Kamble et.al, 2021). These results mirror those from cotton harvesting studies, where farmers reported widespread pain throughout the body due to repetitive and strenuous activities. The next highest prevalence of MSDs was observed in the right and left upper legs, with a mean of 1.28. This suggests that the physical demands of picking during the cabbage harvesting process place significant strain on the upper legs, likely due to the repetitive bending and squatting required to pick and handle the cabbages. In contrast, the right and left lower legs showed the next highest prevalence of MSDs, with a mean of 1.27 each. Similarly, cotton harvesters aged 36-51 reported significant leg symptoms, indicating a higher susceptibility to lower leg MSDs due to prolonged bending and repetitive motions (Kamble et.al, 2022).

In comparison, Boriboonsuksri et al. (2022) investigated the prevalence of MSDs among mango-harvesting farmers using the Borg CR-10 scale to measure perceived physical exertion. Their study highlighted that the right shoulder, right upper arm, and lower back were the most affected areas, likely due to the repetitive motions involved in reaching, lifting, and carrying mangoes. The different patterns of MSD prevalence between cabbage and mango farmers underscore how specific agricultural tasks impose unique physical demands on workers. For cabbage farmers, the frequent squatting and bending actions strain the lower body, while mango farmers experience more upper body strain due to their harvesting techniques. These findings emphasize

the importance of developing ergonomic interventions that are tailored to the specific physical challenges posed by different types of manual agricultural work. By addressing these unique risks, we can help reduce the incidence of MSDs and improve the overall well-being of farmers.

Figure 8. BORG RPE 10 SCALE

C. Using REBA (Rapid Entire Body Assessment)

Table 3. Score using REBA

SPECIFIES	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION
SCORE A		
Neck	2.467	0.67
Trunk	4	0.86
Legs	2.73	0.89
TOTAL	9.197	2.42
SCORE B		
Shoulder	3.07	0.85
Elbow	1.4	0.49
Wrist	2.73	0.63
TOTAL	7.2	1.97

According to the REBA (Rapid Entire Body Assessment) analysis, the highest prevalence of MSD complaints was observed in Score A (shown in table 3), which focuses on the neck, trunk, and legs, with a mean score of 9.197 (SD:2.42) shown in table 3. Based on the results, the most prevalent with a mean of 2.467 was found in the trunk, this issue can be attributed to the repetitive bending and twisting motions required during manual picking of cabbages. These tasks put significant strain on the lower back and core muscles, leading to increased vulnerability to musculoskeletal problems. The legs have a mean of 2.73, which also experience a high prevalence of MSDs, are engaged in prolonged standing, walking, bending and squatting which contribute to muscle fatigue and joint stress. Moreover, the neck experiences the

lowest prevalence because cabbage farmers generally does not involve any activities that required excessive neck strain such as overhead work or prolonged neck extension. The nature of picking cabbages places less demand on the neck compared to the trunk and legs, which bear the brunt of physical labor. This suggests that the physical demands of picking cabbage, which involve repetitive bending, and twisting motions, place considerable strain on these body regions.

Additionally, Score B, which assesses the shoulder, elbow, and wrist, with a mean score of 7.2 (SD: 1.97) shown in table 3, indicating that these upper body parts are less affected during cabbage harvesting. In Score B, the most prevalent score of MSDs was found in the shoulder with a mean of 3.07, which can be link to the repetitive arm movement required for picking cabbages such as handling knife when cutting cabbages. These motions place considerable stress on the shoulder muscles and joints, leading to wear and tear over time. The wrists are also highly affected due to constant gripping, twisting, handling tools and cutting the crops, which can lead to strain in the tendons and joints. On the other hand, the elbow experiences the lowest prevalence of MSD because it tends to be involved in fewer repetitive movements compared to the shoulder and wrist. The elbow's range of motion is less taxed in picking cabbages and making it less susceptible to injury.

In relation to these findings, Solanki and Mehta (2022) noted that different activities in agriculture bring about specific stress and strain on bones and muscles, leading to Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders (WMSDs) that affect various body regions of farmers depending on their occupational tasks. The comparison between these studies underscores how the physical demands of cabbage harvesting, especially through picking, result in notable musculoskeletal strain, particularly in the neck, trunk, and legs. These findings emphasize the need for ergonomic interventions

tailored to the specific demands of cabbage harvesting to mitigate the risk of MSDs and improve the health and productivity of farmers. The results suggest that, like other agricultural tasks, cabbage harvesting involves significant physical challenges that require careful management to prevent long-term musculoskeletal issues.

In conclusion, the study's findings about the perception of MSDs to cabbage farmers underscore the significant physical strain during manual harvesting, particularly in the lower extremities and trunk. The Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ), Borg RPE Scale 10, and Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) were utilized to assess musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) and physical exertion, and the results from all three tools consistently pointed to the hips, thighs, upper legs, and trunk as the primary areas of concern. The NMQ identified 18 cases of MSDs specifically in the hips and thighs, which indicates a high prevalence of discomfort and injury in these regions among the workers. Complementing this, the Borg RPE Scale, which measures perceived exertion, recorded the highest score of 2.47 which observed in the overall part of the body, further highlighting the intense strain these farmers endure. This high level of perceived exertion suggests that the repetitive motions and prolonged periods of bending inherent in manual harvesting are taking a toll on these particular muscle groups.

Moreover, the REBA analysis provided additional insight into the overall postural risks, with a significant focus on the neck, trunk, and legs. The mean REBA Score A of 9.197 indicates a high level of risk associated with the postures adopted during cabbage harvesting, which is reflective of the awkward and sustained positions that farmers must maintain. These findings collectively the physical demands placed on cabbage farmers, particularly in the lower body and trunk, due to the nature of the tasks involved. The repetitive, strenuous work required for manual harvesting not only

increases the risk of musculoskeletal disorders but also suggests a need for interventions, such as ergonomic improvements or mechanization, to alleviate the physical burden on these workers. Ultimately, this study highlights the critical areas of the body that are most vulnerable to strain and injury in cabbage farming, reinforcing the importance of addressing these risks to improve the health and safety of agricultural workers.

IV. Level of Risk Experienced by Cabbage Farmer

The study assessed the risk levels associated with the manual harvesting of cabbage using the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) method. The researchers found out that 30 respondents (100%) were at a very high risk due to their body positions while picking cabbage. The researcher found out that age plays a crucial role in the high-level risk, as shown in the picture (in fig. 9) as older farmers are likely to have reduced muscle strength and joint flexibility, which makes them more susceptible to physical demand when picking cabbages. According to Osborne et al. (2010) older farmers experience and responses to MSDs which the pain is inevitable consequences of farming. With age, the body's ability to recover from such strain diminishes, resulting in an increased risk of MSDs. Furthermore, farmers with greater height face more severe bending angles, as they need to lower their bodies more than shorter cabbage farmers to reach the crops. In figure 10, it proven and shows the score, where is the body part of the older cabbage farmers having very high-risk position in harvesting or picking cabbages. The researcher found out that in trunk and shoulder has the highest score which due to stooped position on picking cabbages. Stooped position often involves prolong bending, which places stress on the lower back, hips, knees, neck and shoulder. Moreover, maintaining stooped position can

lead to discomfort, fatigue, and the development of MSDs, particularly on their lower extremities.

Figure 9. Very High-Risk Position

REBA Method Find the full guide here

Name: _____ First name: _____ Date: _____
 Workstation: _____

A. Neck, trunk and legs analysis

Step 1 Locate neck position
 Neck in lateral flexion: Add +1
 Neck in axial rotation: Add +1
 Score: 3

Step 2 Locate trunk position
 Trunk in axial rotation: Add +1
 Trunk in lateral flexion: Add +1
 Score: 4

Step 3 Legs
 ADJUSTMENTS:
 Flexion is between 30° and 60°: Add +1
 Flexion is greater than 60°: Add +2
 Legs are in broodial support: +1
 Legs are in monopodal support: +2
 Score: 4

Step 4 Posture Score A
 Using the values from steps 1 to 3, find the score in table A.
 Score: 9

Trunk	Neck				Legs			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
1	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
2	2	3	4	5	3	4	5	6
3	2	4	5	6	4	5	6	7
4	3	4	5	6	5	6	7	8
5	4	5	6	7	6	7	8	9

Step 5 Effort and load score
 Load less than 5kg: 0
 Load between 5kg and 10kg: +1
 Load greater than 10kg: +2
 If a brace, vest, posture change or high repetitiveness: Add +1
 Score: 0

Step 6 Neck, trunk and legs score
 Add the values from steps 4 to 5 to obtain the Neck, Trunk and Legs score corresponding to the rows in table C.
 Score: 9

Table B

Shoulder	Elbow				Wrist			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
1	1	2	2	1	2	3		
2	1	2	3	2	3	4		
3	3	4	5	5	5	5		
4	3	4	4	4	6	7	8	9
5	6	7	8	7	8	9		
6	7	8	8	8	9	9		

Table C

Neck, Trunk, Legs	Shoulder, Elbow, Wrist											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	1	1	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	7	8
2	1	2	2	3	4	4	5	6	6	7	7	8
3	2	3	3	3	4	5	6	7	7	8	8	9
4	3	4	4	4	5	6	7	8	8	9	9	9
5	4	4	4	5	5	6	7	8	8	9	9	9
6	6	6	6	7	8	8	9	9	10	10	10	10
7	7	7	7	8	9	9	10	10	10	11	11	11
8	8	8	8	9	10	10	10	10	11	11	11	11
9	9	9	9	10	10	10	11	11	11	12	12	12
10	10	10	10	11	11	11	12	12	12	12	12	12
11	11	11	11	11	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12

Step 13 Score C
 Using the values from steps 6 and 12, find the score in table C.
 Score: 12

Step 14 Activity score
 If the posture is static (>= 1min): Add +1
 If the posture is repeated more than 4 times per minute: Add +1
 If there is a quick and wide change of posture or unstable base: Add +1
 Score: 2

B. Shoulder, elbow and wrist analysis

Step 7 Locate shoulder position
 Shoulder raised: Add +1
 Shoulder abducted: Add +1
 If the shoulder is supported or the person is leaning: Remove -1
 Score: 4

Step 8 Locate elbow position
 Score: 2

Step 9 Locate wrist position
 If ulnar/radial wrist deviation: Add +1
 Score: 1

Step 10 Posture Score B
 Using the values from steps 7 to 9, find the score in table B.
 Score: 5

Step 11 Grip score
 The hand hold is good with handles: 0
 The hand hold is acceptable: Add +1
 The hand hold is not acceptable but possible: Add +2
 The hand hold is dangerous: Add +3
 Score: 0

Step 12 Shoulder, elbow and wrist score
 Add the values from steps 10 to 11 to obtain the Shoulder, Elbow and Wrist score corresponding to the columns in table C.
 Score: 5

REBA final score

Table C score + Activity score: 12 + 2 = 14

Score	Risk level
1	Negligible risk = no action required.
2-3	Low risk = change may be required.
4-7	Medium risk = vigilance, improvements to consider.
8-12	High risk = improvements needed.
>12	Very high risk = immediate response.

Score: 14
Risk level: High risk = improvements needed.

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Figure 10. Very High-Risk Score

The researcher also found out that there is no permanent position of the cabbage farmers when picking cabbages, it changes when they twisting to pick and reach cabbage. Harvesting cabbages involves reaching, bending, and handling the cabbages at various angles and heights, requiring farmers that adopt awkward postures. The need to access cabbages spread out in rows forces them to twist their bodies to reach plants that are not directly in front of them, which helps same time and effort. This movement reduces the need to walk around each cabbage, but it often results repetitive strain on their muscles and joints. Additionally, the act of cutting the cabbage stem, lifting the heavy heads, and trimming the outer leaves requires cabbage farmers to use twisting motions to work efficiently. The limited space between the cabbages can also contributes to twisting, as farmers have to manoeuvre in confined areas without disturbing other crops. However, these repetitive and awkward movements, if done continuously, can lead to the development of MSD, making it an important issue to address for the health and well-being of cabbage farmers.

Figure 11. Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA)

During the data collection process using the Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire, Rapid Entire Body Assessment, and Borg RPE Scale 10, respondents reported that they are experiencing discomfort in almost all body parts while working as cabbage farmers. Despite the seemingly simple task of picking cabbage, the repetitive nature of the work leads to significant strain on the body. The most affected areas are the hips, which endure stress from frequent bending motions. The knees also bear substantial pressure, as they support the entire body weight during prolonged periods of crouching or kneeling. Additionally, the wrists face considerable strain due to the continuous movement required for picking cabbage, which involves both ulnar and radial wrist deviation.

This repetitive strain contributes to the development of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) in these farmers. The physical demands of the job exacerbate fatigue and discomfort, making the task more physically taxing than it initially appears. The data collected highlights the need for ergonomic interventions to alleviate these strains and reduce the risk of MSDs among cabbage farmers. Proper equipment and techniques could potentially mitigate some of the discomfort experienced. Understanding these physical demands is crucial for developing strategies to improve the working conditions and overall health of farmers engaged in manual harvesting tasks. Manual harvesting of cabbage contributes to the MSDs experienced by the cabbage farmers due to repetitive movements specifically in manual picking of cabbage. Overall health of the cabbage farmers in manual harvesting is considered strenuous for their body regions and requires several improvements in the technique and how much time interval is needed for them to take a rest, as to not stress out every muscle region in their bodies. The cabbage farmers despite being used to these MSDs, does not mean that their situation should be neglected. Further research for

improvements is a vital step to introducing new ways to avoid MSDs and improve productivity in manual picking of cabbage during harvesting.

CHAPTER 3

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendation of the study.

Summary of Findings

The findings specifically identified which part of the body regions must likely affected when picking cabbages during harvest season of the cabbage farmers which due to awkward postures in bending, twisting, squatting, and kneeling. The researcher highlights the significant physical strain experienced by cabbage farmers during manual harvesting, particularly affecting the lower extremities and trunk. Using Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (NMQ), it was found that the hips/thighs had the highest prevalence of discomfort (18 cases), while the lower back had the lowest (7 cases). The Borg RPE Scale, which measures perceived exertion, recorded the highest score of 2.47 which is observed in the overall part of the body, further highlighting the intense strain these farmers endure. The Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) showed that complaints were most prevalent in the neck, trunk, and legs (Score A: mean of 7.17), with the shoulders, elbows, and wrists also affected but to a lesser degree (Score B: mean of 4.867). Furthermore, the researcher found out using REBA which indicated that 100% of the farmers are at very high-risk during cabbage picking. Overall health of the cabbage farmers in manual harvesting is considered strenuous for their body regions and requires several improvements in the technique as to not stress out every muscle region in their bodies. Moreover, these results highlight the critical areas of the body that are highly vulnerable to strain and injury among cabbage farmers which can be a risk to their safety and health. In

addition, addressing research intervention for cabbage farmers is vital to avoid MSD and to maintain and improve their productivity on manual harvesting of cabbages.

According to the study's findings, various factors, including age, height, weight, experience, and gender, contribute to musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) among cabbage farmers. The mean age of 32.23 years is significantly younger than the average farmer's age in the Philippines, suggesting a generational shift that could influence MSD patterns. The higher susceptibility of older farmers to work-related MSDs due to factors such as decreased muscle strength, endurance, and overall functional capacity, making them more vulnerable to injuries. These findings highlight the importance of considering age-related differences when assessing MSD risks in the agricultural sector. The mean height of 155 cm requires more bending and stooping during manual harvesting, increasing the risk of lower back pain and other MSDs. Furthermore, farmers with greater height face more severe bending angles, as they need to lower their bodies more than shorter cabbage farmers to reach the crops. The average weight of 56.27 kg, with a range of 43 kg to 73 kg, indicates that heavier farmers may experience more strain when bending, heightening the risk of MSDs. Experience plays a role, as experienced farmers may develop better techniques to minimize strain, but prolonged exposure to repetitive tasks can still lead to MSDs. Gender differences also influence MSD prevalence, with women potentially experiencing different MSD patterns due to physiological differences and task types.

Moreover, the researchers discovered that some cabbage farmers chose to work hard or spend more time harvesting cabbages even though they experience MSDs because farming is their only source of income and provides for the needs and wants of their families. According to Jo et al. (2016), MSDs are more frequent among farmers, with more severe symptoms affecting the hands and forearms, lower back,

and hips compared to less physically demanding non-farmer occupations, which can substantially impact and result in long-term disability and income loss. With these results and findings, the researchers underscore the need for interventions, such as ergonomic improvements, adequate rest intervals to avoid stressing every muscle region, and mechanization, to reduce the physical burden on farmers and improve their health and safety.

Conclusion

The study conducted a comprehensive analysis of Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs) among cabbage farmers engaged in manual harvesting. The findings revealed that the most prevalent MSDs were experienced in the hips/thighs, followed by the lower back, shoulders, and knees. The use of ergonomic assessment tools such as the REBA, NMQ, and Borg RPE Scale was crucial in identifying these risk factors.

Postural and musculoskeletal problems have become endemic in agriculture work. The workers usually complain about pain in various parts of the body most especially in the neck, shoulder, trunk and leg region. The maximum was reported very severe to severe pain in the left and right leg while picking cabbage because they are untrained, uneducated, unaware about different innovative agriculture practices or right postural on harvesting. Repetitive motions, overexertion, long hours of work, continuous and forceful motions, and bending awkward postures are some of the main causes which attributes to many occupational musculoskeletal disorders of picking cabbage.

Interventions to reduce the risk of MSDs could include ergonomic training for farmers, the introduction of mechanical aids to reduce manual labour, and regular breaks to alleviate strain. Additionally, policy changes aimed at improving working conditions and providing protective equipment could significantly lower the risk levels.

The level of risk hazard for farmers during cabbage picking was found to be substantial, with a majority at very high risk according to REBA scores. This highlights the urgent need for targeted interventions to protect the health and well-being of these essential workers in our agricultural sector.

Recommendation

Farmers are crucial to our community, especially cabbage farmers who experience musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) during the manual picking of cabbage during harvest season. MSDs are one of the most relevant occupational diseases in the agricultural sector, caused by high numbers of manual tasks and sudden or sustained exposure to force, vibration, repetitive motion, and awkward postures such as sitting, bending, kneeling, twisting, and squatting (Benos et al., 2020; Steven et al., 2010). To address this, it is essential to provide training and education for those farmers who are less knowledgeable about the effects of various awkward postures during harvesting cabbage which further develops MSDs among manual farmers (Jain et al., 2018). Implementing structured work schedules that incorporate regular breaks and task rotation can help alleviate repetitive strain and mitigate the risk of musculoskeletal injuries. Additionally, health and wellness programs that promote physical resilience through targeted exercises can further reduce the occurrence of work-related musculoskeletal ailments.

Future research should focus on exploring innovative strategies to minimize the risk of MSDs in agricultural settings. This may include in-depth studies on ergonomic work practices, improved harvesting techniques, and alternative methods that reduce physical strain. Investigating the long-term effects of MSDs on farmers' productivity and well-being will also be valuable in developing evidence-based interventions. By expanding on this research, future studies can contribute to the development of effective solutions that improve the occupational health and overall productivity of cabbage farmers, ensuring a safer and more sustainable agricultural workforce.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) Worksheet

REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Task Name:

Date:

A. Neck, Trunk and Leg Analysis

Step 1: Locate Neck Position

Step 1a: Adjust...
If neck is twisted: +1
If neck is side bending: +1

Neck Score

Step 2: Locate Trunk Position

Step 2a: Adjust...
If trunk is twisted: +1
If trunk is side bending: +1

Trunk Score

Step 3: Legs

Adjust:

Leg Score

Step 4: Look-up Posture Score in Table A

Using values from steps 1-3 above,
Locate score in Table A

Posture Score A

Step 5: Add Force/Load Score

If load < 11 lbs.: +0
If load 11 to 22 lbs.: +1
If load > 22 lbs.: +2

Adjust: If shock or rapid build up of force: add +1

Force / Load Score

Step 6: Score A, Find Row in Table C

Add values from steps 4 & 5 to obtain Score A.
Find Row in Table C.

Score A

Scoring

- 1 = Negligible Risk
- 2-3 = Low Risk. Change may be needed.
- 4-7 = Medium Risk. Further Investigate. Change Soon.
- 8-10 = High Risk. Investigate and Implement Change
- 11+ = Very High Risk. Implement Change

Scores

Table A		Neck											
		1			2			3					
Legs		1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Trunk		1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	3	3	5	6
Posture		2	2	3	4	5	3	4	5	6	4	5	6
Score		3	2	4	5	6	4	5	6	7	5	6	7
		4	3	5	6	7	5	6	7	8	6	7	8
		5	4	6	7	8	6	7	8	9	7	8	9

B. Arm and Wrist Analysis

Step 7: Locate Upper Arm Position:

Step 7a: Adjust...
If shoulder is raised: +1
If upper arm is abducted: +1
If arm is supported or person is leaning: -1

Upper Arm Score

Step 8: Locate Lower Arm Position:

Lower Arm Score

Step 9: Locate Wrist Position:

Wrist Score

Step 9a: Adjust...
If wrist is bent from midline or twisted: Add +1

Step 10: Look-up Posture Score in Table B

Using values from steps 7-9 above, locate score in Table B

Posture Score B

Step 11: Add Coupling Score

- Well fitting Handle and mid range power grip, **good: +0**
- Acceptable but not ideal hand hold or coupling acceptable with another body part, **fair: +1**
- Hand hold not acceptable but possible, **poor: +2**
- No handles, awkward, unsafe with any body part, **Unacceptable: +3**

Coupling Score

Step 12: Score B, Find Column in Table C

Add values from steps 10 & 11 to obtain Score B. Find column in Table C and match with Score A in row from step 6 to obtain Table C Score.

Score B

Step 13: Activity Score

- +1 1 or more body parts are held for longer than 1 minute (static)
- +1 Repeated small range actions (more than 4x per minute)
- +1 Action causes rapid large range changes in postures or unstable base

Score A	Table C											
	Score B											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	1	1	1	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	7	7
2	1	2	2	3	4	4	5	6	6	7	7	8
3	2	3	3	3	4	5	6	7	7	8	8	8
4	3	4	4	4	5	6	7	8	8	9	9	9
5	4	4	4	5	6	7	8	8	9	9	9	9
6	6	6	6	7	8	8	9	9	10	10	10	10
7	7	7	7	8	9	9	10	10	11	11	11	11
8	8	8	8	9	10	10	10	10	11	11	11	11
9	9	9	9	10	10	10	11	11	11	12	12	12
10	10	10	10	11	11	11	11	12	12	12	12	12
11	11	11	11	11	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12

Table C Score + Activity Score = REBA Score

APPENDIX B

Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaire

Musculoskeletal Discomfort Form (Based on the Nordic Questionnaire (Kourinka et al. 1987))

Employee ID: _____

Job/Position: _____ Gender: M F Age: _____ Height: ___ ft. ___ in. Weight: _____

How long have you been doing this job? ___ years ___ months How many hours do you work each week? _____

How to answer the questionnaire:

Picture: In this picture you can see the approximate position of the parts of the body referred to in the table. Limits are not sharply defined, and certain parts overlap. You should decide for yourself in which part you have or have had your trouble (if any).

Table: Please answer by putting an "X" in the appropriate box - one "X" for each question. You may be in doubt as to how to answer, but please do your best anyway. Note that column 1 of the questionnaire is to be answered even if you have never had trouble in any part of your body; columns 2 and 3 are to be answered if you answered yes in column 1.

To be answered by everyone	To be answered by those who have had trouble	
Have you at any time during the last 12 months had trouble (ache, pain, discomfort, numbness) in:	Have you at any time during the last 12 months been prevented from doing your normal work (at home or away from home) because of the trouble?	Have you had trouble at any time during the last 7 days?
Neck <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
Shoulders <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, right shoulder <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, left shoulder <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, both shoulders	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
Elbows <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, right elbow <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, left elbow <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, both elbows	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
Wrists/Hands <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, right wrist/hand <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, left wrist/hand <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, both wrists/hands	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
Upper Back <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
Lower Back (small of back) <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
One or Both Hips/Thighs <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
One or Both Knees <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes
One or Both Ankles/Feet <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes

APPENDIX C

BORG RPE 10 SCALE

0	Nothing at all
0.5	Extremely weak
1	Very Weak
2	Weak
3	Moderate
4	Somewhat intense
5	Intense
6	
7	Very Intense
8	
9	
10	Excruciating

1 Head		9 Lower Back		17 Left wrist	
2 Face		10 Right Shoulder		18 Right Upper Leg	
3 Neck		11 Left Shoulder		19 Left Upper Leg	
4 Chest		12 Right Upper Arm		20 Right Lower Leg	
5 Mid Torso –Waist		13 Left Upper Arm		21 Left Lower Leg	
6 Lower Torso		14 Right Lower Arm		22 Right ankle	
7 Upper Back		15 Left Lower Arm		23 Left ankle	
8 Mid Back		16 Right Wrist		24 Overall	

CURRICULUM

VITAE

Personal Information:

Name: KRISTYL S. DIAZ

Age: 21 years old

Gender: Female

Date of Birth: December 20, 2002

Civil Status: Single

Religion: Roman Catholic

Place of Birth: Taytay, Badian, Cebu

Father's Name: Agustin B. Diaz

Mother's Name: Nemesia S. Diaz

Home Address: Basak, Badian, Cebu

Educational Attainment:

TERTIARY: CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY – MOALBOAL CAMPUS

Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu

Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering

S.Y. 2021-Present

SENIOR HIGH: BADIAN NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

Poblacion, Badian, Cebu

S.Y. 2020-2021

JUNIOR HIGH: BADIAN NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

Poblacion, Badian, Cebu

S.Y. 2018-2019

PRIMARY: BADIAN CENTRAL SCHOOL

Poblacion, Badian, Cebu

S.Y. 2014-2015

Personal Information:

Name: SHERLYN O. CARCELLER

Age: 20 years old

Gender: Female

Date of Birth: June 3, 2003

Civil Status: Single

Religion: Roman Catholic

Place of Birth: Sta.Cruz, Metro Manila

Father's Name: Cerwin C. Carceller

Mother's Name: Florenda O. Carceller

Educational Attainment:

TERTIARY: CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY – MOALBOAL CAMPUS

Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu

Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering

S.Y. 2021-Present

SENIOR HIGH: SAINT PETER ACADEMY OF ALEGRIA, INC.

Poblacion Alegria, Cebu

S.Y. 2020-2021

JUNIOR HIGH: SORSOGON NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

Sorsogon, Malabuyoc, Cebu

S.Y. 2018-2019

PRIMARY: SORSOGON ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

Sorsogon, Malabuyoc, Cebu

S.Y. 2014-2015

Personal Information:

Name: MARK KIM T. PERALES

Age: 21 years old

Gender: Male

Date of Birth: October 4, 2002

Civil Status: Single

Religion: Roman Catholic

Place of Birth: Tagbilaran City

Father's Name: Tereso Jamsey T. Perales

Mother's Name Nielisa T. Perales

Home Address: Purok Pakigbisog, Poblacion, Alcantara, Cebu

Educational Attainment:

TERTIARY: CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY – MOALBOAL CAMPUS

Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu

Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering

S.Y. 2021-Present

SENIOR HIGH: Corella National High School

Poblacion Corella, Bohol

S.Y. 2020-2021

JUNIOR HIGH: Corella National High School

Poblacion Corella, Bohol

S.Y. 2018-2019

PRIMARY: Corella National High School

Poblacion, Corella, Bohol

S.Y. 2014-2015

Personal Information:

Name: GRECEL NIÑO QUISAOT

Age: 25 years old

Gender: Male

Date of Birth: July 13, 1999

Civil Status: Single

Religion: Roman Catholic

Place of Birth: Basdiot, Moalboal, Cebu

Father's Name: Deceased

Mother's Name: Cirila T. Quisaot

Home Address: Purok Palata, Basdiot, Moalboal, Cebu

Educational Attainment:

TERTIARY: CEBU TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY – MOALBOAL CAMPUS

Poblacion West, Moalboal, Cebu

Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering

S.Y. 2021-Present

SENIOR HIGH: Moalboal National High School

Basdiot, Moalboal, Cebu

S.Y. 2020-2021

JUNIOR HIGH: Moalboal National High School

Basdiot, Moalboal, Cebu

S.Y. 2018-2019

PRIMARY: Basdiot Elementary School

Basdiot, Moalboal, Cebu

S.Y. 2014-2015